

THE ROLE OF MEDIA AND INFORMATIONAL EDUCATION IN THE TRAINING OF CIVIL ENGINEERS

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ANNOTATION

The article examines the formation of a specialist as a comprehensively developed, humane personality and the features of his competence. Using the methods of system analysis, the state of competency characteristics was assessed by observation, and the corresponding conclusions were formed through abstract logical thinking.

Keywords: *competence, effectiveness of actions, professional activity, professional activity, psychological and pedagogical, knowledge, skills*

INTRODUCTION. The world's construction industry is experiencing rapid changes due to the adoption of new technologies and processes. As a result, it is critical for future civil engineers to acquire the technological skills necessary to succeed in this dynamic environment.

The construction industry is increasingly complex and demanding, and new technologies and processes are constantly being introduced. To overcome this complexity, future civil engineers must have a solid foundation in technology, understanding and implementing the latest technologies such as building information modeling (BIM), computer-aided design (CAD) and augmented reality (AR). This creates the need to develop the technological competence of civil engineers in an informational educational environment.

In addition, technological competence can provide a competitive advantage in the construction industry. In a highly competitive market, those with the most advanced technological skills are more likely to win new contracts and clients. This is especially important in an industry where innovation and efficiency are critical to success. The need for the integration of educational processes requires the formation of an open information-educational environment, which allows: to take the educational process outside the educational institution; establishment of large educational consortia; creating global libraries of educational resources; to ensure adaptation of future specialists to new working conditions in the global information space. Accordingly, by developing the technological competence of future engineers-builders, logical thinking and the formation of necessary competencies in finding solutions to professional problems occupy an important place.

PF-4947 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 " On the Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" , PQ-2909 dated April 20, 2017 "On Measures for the Further Development of the Higher Education System", Decree No. PF-5349 of February 19, 2018 "On measures to further improve the field of information technologies and communications" , No. PQ-3775 of June 5, 2018 "Increasing the quality of education in higher education institutions and their promotion in the country "On additional measures to ensure active participation in comprehensive reforms" dated October 6, 2020 PQ-4851 "Further improvement of the educational system in the field of information technology, development of scientific research and their integration with the IT industry" on measures to be taken" dated August 31, 2021 No. PQ-5241 "On measures to strengthen the continuity of the educational process and production practice between higher, secondary special and professional educational institutions" and this activity Tasks defined in other normative legal documents on i show that there is still a lot of work to be done in this area.

The inclusion of BIM technology in design reduces financial costs and significantly shortens the period of commissioning of the facility. Therefore, most

construction companies try to use modern information modeling methods in their practice.

CONCLUSION. Refers to an intelligent three-dimensional model created in virtual space to visualize architectural design, construction, or facility management data using digital software tools.

This digital model can be called a product resulting from the aforementioned business process.

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